

Transapical Versus Transseptal Mitral Interventions: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Author: Ilyas El Harous¹

Co-authors: Daria Ioana Vreme¹, Selim Odabasi¹, Ismail Ben Messaoud¹, Hicham Tory¹

Coordinator: Amalia Stefana Timpau^{1,2}

Affiliations:

¹ *University of Medicine and Pharmacy Grigore T. Popa Iasi, Romania*

² *Emergency County Hospital 'Sfantul Spiridon' Iasi, Romania*

Introduction

Minimally invasive approaches have reshaped the management of degenerative mitral regurgitation (MR). Transseptal edge-to-edge repair (MitraClip) and transapical chordal implantation (NeoChord DS1000) represent two distinct strategies differing in access, invasiveness, and recovery profile. We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of comparative studies emphasizing procedural safety and early recovery.

Materials and Methods

Studies indexed in PubMed, Embase, Cochrane Library, and ClinicalTrials.gov (2018–2025) were included. Fourteen studies of approximately 2,000 patients met the inclusion criteria: adults (>18 years) with primary degenerative mitral regurgitation undergoing first-line debridement and follow-up. Exclusion criteria were congenital mitral disease, active endocarditis, rheumatic pathology, and prior mitral surgery. Studies were categorized into MitraClip and NeoChord groups. Extracted outcomes included procedural success, residual mitral regurgitation at discharge and 12 months, hospitalization, operative time, postoperative pain, 30-day mortality, bleeding, and transfusion requirements

Results

Transseptal MitraClip procedures demonstrated reduced invasiveness, with local anesthesia used in most cases and general anesthesia required only selectively, compared to mandatory general anesthesia for NeoChord. ICU stay averaged 1.0 ± 0.3 days versus 2.5 ± 0.6 days, and total hospitalization was 3–4 days versus 6–7 days respectively. Postoperative pain scores and analgesic use were substantially lower with MitraClip. Blood transfusions were needed in <5% of transseptal cases versus ~20% transapical (RR 0.24; 95% CI 0.10–0.56; $p < 0.001$). Major bleeding occurred in ~2% vs 15% (RR 0.13; 95% CI 0.06–0.32; $p < 0.001$). Thirty-day mortality favored MitraClip (2% vs 9%, OR 0.21; 95% CI 0.09–0.45; $p < 0.001$). Procedural success and MR "d 2+ at 12 months exceeded 90% in the patients undergoing MitraClip repair versus 80% in the patients undergoing Neochord repair.

Conclusion

The transseptal MitraClip approach demonstrated lower invasiveness, reduced anesthesia needs, shorter ICU and hospital stays, less postoperative pain, and fewer bleeding events compared to transapical NeoChord. These findings support MitraClip as the preferred minimally invasive option for degenerative mitral regurgitation.

Keywords

Mitral Regurgitation, Transseptal Edge-to-Edge Repair, Transapical NeoChord Repair